

Fair Data and Innovative Services for
Magnifying the Climate Adaptation
potential of European Communities

ClimateAdapt4EOSC

D1.2 – Project specification, Architecture and
KPIs

Deliverable Information Sheet

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List of Acronyms

IF	Interoperability Framework
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
UC	Use Case
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDAnalytics	Big Data Analytics
CNN	Convolution Neural Network
CV	Computer Vision
DL	Deep Learning
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reuseable
GUI	Graphical User Interface
LLM	Large Language Model
LVM	Large Vision Model
ML	Machine Learning
MMDS	Multimodal Multi-Domain Self-supervised (Model)
PID	Persistent Identifier
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SoTA	State-of-the-Art
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
AP	Application Profile
API	Application Programming Interface
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

CSW	Catalogue Services for the Web
RBAC	Role-based access control
GIS	Geographic Information System
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
NBS	Natural Based Solutions

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1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

The CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC project is aimed to integrate, manage, and make accessible climate data sourced from across Europe by implementing cutting-edge interoperability frameworks and FAIR data principles. Its architecture consists of both open and federated data sources integration, a middleware platform for authentication and federation, and a FAIRification pipeline that ensures standardized metadata, cross-domain interoperability, and technical, semantic, legal, and organizational harmonisation. The standardise data will be used to develop and provide four novel climate adaptation services (BDAnalytics, OPENHIDRA, 3SES, Just-CURS).

This deliverable explains an architecture designed to handle climate data across national and international data sources and make it more useful for everyone. It specifies how various climate datasets and derived products are standardised, processed, and made FAIR-compliant for broad reusability. The document serves to establish the foundation for key project components, including data transformation schemas, interoperability strategies spanning multiple domains, and service integration within the EOOSC ecosystem.

The project is built around two main parts (Figure 2):

- **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC:** This part collects climate data, puts it into a standard format, and checks it meets FAIR principles (making sure the data is easy to find, read, share and use by others). Using SIMPL-Open Middleware and SMP Agents, all ingested information will be standardised, FAIR-compliant.
- **CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOOSC:** This part creates four practical tools - BDAnalytics, OPENHIDRA, 3SES and Just-CURS. They use new methods, big data and computer simulations. All the information they work with comes from the CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC service, which collects, organises and shares climate data that follows FAIR rules.

Figure 1 Climate-Adapt4EOOSC Key Components

This architecture helps manage climate data and build useful services so that anyone can work better together and make decisions for a more climate-resilient future.

This deliverable includes a detailed **KPI (Key Performance Indicator)** registry, which sets out clear goals and measures for the project's success. The registry covers important areas such as documentation standards, data quality, and security of information. The KPI registry will help project partners identify achievements, highlight areas that need improvement, and ensure full accountability throughout the life of **CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC**.

1.2. How this deliverable is organised

This deliverable is organised into a sequence of structured chapters, beginning with

- Chapter 2 – Climate-Adapt4EOOSC System Architecture presents the overall system overview, key performance indicators (KPIs), and the architectural design.
- Chapter 3 – Data Sources categorises the various types of data sources and describes the authentication procedures and federated access mechanisms.
- Chapter 4 – Integration with Data Spaces & Data Sources introduces Simpl-Open, Simpl Open (SMP) Agents, and clarifies the roles of Data Providers and Data Consumers.
- Chapter 5 – Common Middleware Platform details the middleware design, including authentication, authorisation, the federated access catalogue, and the metadata flow.
- Chapter 6 – FAIRification Pipeline & Interoperability outlines the data harmonisation process, covering the FAIRification template, metadata standards,

- and the technical, semantic, legal, and organisational interoperability workflows.
- Chapter 7 – Intermediate Schema explains the data transformation and storage model.
 - Chapter 8 – CLIMATE-ADAPT0/4EOSC describes the core data platform, including the query service, Simpl-Open SMP Agent functionality, user access patterns, and the FAIR Publisher Service.
 - Chapter 9 – CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOSC presents the four climate adaptation services (Just-CURS, OPENHIDRA, 3SES, and BDAalytics) and their system, data, and application architectures.
 - Chapter 10 – EOSC Integration details the architecture alignment with EOSC, the establishment of a dedicated EOSC node, and options for onboarding into existing EOSC nodes.
 - Chapter 11 – CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC KPI Definition defines the project's performance framework and maps KPIs to each work package.
 - Chapter 12 – Risk and mitigation measure summarises key technical and organisational risks and the mitigation strategies related to the middleware, FAIRification pipeline, and EOSC onboarding.
 - Chapter 13 – Conclusion provides final reflections on the project architecture, KPI framework, and planned future work within CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC.

2. Climate-Adapt4EOSC System Architecture

2.1. System Architecture

The Climate-Adapt4EOSC system architecture brings together climate data, processing, and services through several connected components. Each part plays a special role to make sure climate information is managed securely, shared effectively, and turned into useful tools for users across Europe. Figure 2 is a demonstration of a comprehensive architecture consisting of following components -

- **Data Sources:** Places where climate data is collected, such as catalogues and services.
- **Simpl Open (SMP) Agents:** Act as both providers and consumers, managing access to the data and passing it through the system.
- **SIMPL-Open Middleware:** Handles user authentication, collects a catalogue of resources, and stores them in a data repository.
- **FAIRification Pipeline:** Prepares all data using clear standards, templates, and best practices so climate information is easy to find and share.
- **Interoperability Framework (IF):** Covers technical, semantic, legal, and organisational checks to ensure data can work together from different sources for standardising the data.
- **Intermediate Schema:** Data will be transformed into an intermediate schema before saving into a PostgreSQL² database (including PostGIS³ extension enabled). These will be used for performing SPARQL query while querying standardise data.
- **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOSC:** The entry point where the output of FAIRification pipeline arrives and will be distributed across other components like Climate-AdaptService4ESOC and FAIR Publisher Service.

² <https://www.postgresql.org/>

³ <https://postgis.net/>

- Query Service:** Allows users to make requests and get standardise data from the system, by performing SPARQL query, managed through Simpl Open (SMP) Agents.

Figure 2 Climate-Adapt4EOOSC System Architecture

- FAIR Publisher Service:** Will be responsible for publishing FAIR data into EOOSC Node.
- Climate-Adaptservice4EOOSC:** Provides 4 novel tools for users, including BDAnalytics, Just-CURS, OPENHIDRA, and 3SES. These tools take FAIR output from the FAIRification pipeline via CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC.

This system ensures that climate adaptation data is standardised, secure, and ready to support decision-making and collaboration. This architecture was designed with the aim of supporting the main objectives of the CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC project.

3. Data Sources

3.1. Data Source Types

The three cases (UC1 - Just-CURS, UC2 - OPENHIDRA, UC3 - 3SES) rely on a mix of data spaces and data sources. These provide both scientific datasets and operational information needed for climate adaptation and risk management. Additionally other data sources have been explored to identify more relevant data sources for Climate-Adapt4EOSC.

To provide a clear picture of the data environment used in Climate-Adapt4EOSC, this deliverable summarises the main types of data sources that support the all three use cases of this project (JUST-Curs, OPENHIDRA, 3SES). These include the specific data spaces and repositories directly used by the UC partners which was prepared under Task 1.3; the broader EU Common Data Spaces that represent the reference landscape for European data governance; and a range of national and international data providers such as meteorological agencies, marine institutes, scientific repositories, and Earth observation services. Together, these categories show the diversity of data sources involved in the project and help highlight where alignment and harmonisation will be needed in later work.

Table 1 Summary of Different Data Sources investigated for Climate-Adapt4EOSC

Category	Examples	Description / Notes
Use Case Data Spaces & Sources	NCSRD Internal Space, NOA Internal Space, OPENCoasts, EGL GIS (Municipality of Egaleo), ELSTAT, CoolScape datasets, Hidrografico Boias Network	Concrete, operational sources used directly by UC1 (Aigaleo & West Athens), UC2 (OPENHIDRA) and UC3 (3SES). Includes internal repositories, municipal GIS systems, national statistical agencies, marine buoy networks, and use-case-specific model outputs.
EU Common Data Spaces	Green Deal Dataspace, Agriculture Dataspace, Energy Dataspace, Mobility Dataspace, Manufacturing Dataspace, EO SC family (FAIRiCUBE, FAIRCORE4EOSC,	Cross-domain European data spaces aligned with EU Data Strategy. Provide conceptual reference for governance, interoperability (DCAT-AP, ODRL, FAIR), and federated access mechanisms (e.g., IDS,

	AI4EOSC), Dataspace	Tourism	GAIA-X). Used as a benchmark in D1.1 and contrasted here in D1.2.
National & International Data Providers	Copernicus (Atmosphere, Marine, Land), ECMWF, IPMA, NOAA, NCAR/UCAR WRF Repository, Zenodo, CMMG Buoy System, BRGM (Infoterre), ESRI/ESDAC, NASA (GRACE), MeteoFrance, FAO AQUAMAPS		Large-scale environmental, meteorological, geospatial, and scientific data services used by the use cases in addition to EU data spaces. These include both open-access and restricted-access platforms, covering climate reanalysis, marine observations, soil data, groundwater data, and more.

3.2. Authentication & Federated Access of Different Data Sources

The data sources identified for the Climate-Adapt4EOSC that indicates that use cases rely on a mixture of open, restricted, and federated access mechanisms. Many publicly available platforms (such as Copernicus, Zenodo, NOAA, or several national open-data portals) can be accessed freely or through basic user registration. Other scientific services require authenticated access via API keys, institutional accounts, or controlled agreements (e.g., ECMWF, IPMA, Hydrografico Institute). In parallel, EU Common Data Spaces are introducing more advanced federated access models based on frameworks such as GAIA-X, IDS connectors, and DAPS trust services.

Because Climate-Adapt4EOSC integrates data from all three categories, use-case-specific sources, EU Data Spaces, and national/international services, the project must accommodate multiple access and authentication pathways. This includes direct APIs, manual downloads, internal repositories, and future connections to federated data spaces through Simpl-Open Agents and the Middleware Platform. Table 2 categorises the different data sources and demonstrates data access mechanisms.

Table 2 Data Sources and Authorisation and Access Mechanism

Data Source Category	Data Acquisition Options	How Data Is Accessed
Use Case Data Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internal portals API 	Some of them are private or semi-private, may require

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File transfer <p>Restricted access via institutional login</p>	authentication agreements or permissions.
EU Common Data Spaces	Federated Access via IDS Connectors, GAIA-X, DAPS	Future integration with Simpl-Open Middleware Platform
National & International Data Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export using Catalogue • API Download <p>Manual Integration</p>	Access may be restricted to approved users or research projects. For some provider, manual integration needed

4. Integration with Data Spaces & Data Sources

The first step in our approach is to bring various data sources into FAIRification pipeline to standardise into a form where they can be accessed and worked with in a consistent way. Although all participating dataspace already provide FAIR metadata, the way this information is exposed is not uniform. Some follow recognised catalogue standards such as **DCAT-AP**⁴, **OAI-PMH** or **CSW**, while others rely on internal APIs that publish metadata in formats like **JSON**, **XML** or even simple CSV files.

To manage this variation, we set up a **Simple-Open Agent**⁵ for each dataspace. The Simpl Open (SMP) Agent uses a connector such as **Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC)**⁶ to facilitate secure and trustworthy connections to various data sources. For catalogues that are openly accessible, this is a straightforward fetch. Where catalogues require authentication, the agent takes care of the login and authorisation steps. This keeps the process compatible with the **Gaia-X**⁷ model of trust and identity.

4.1. Simpl-Open - An EU Initiative

Simpl-Open emerged as part of the European Commission's Simpl programme, which was initiated to enable interoperable digital public services and cross-border data sharing within the EU. It is an open, standards-based framework, provides a common structure for how data should be shared, accessed, and interpreted, reducing the need for custom integrations and helping organisations connect their services more efficiently. By defining consistent models, APIs, and operational patterns, Simpl-Open ensures that information can move smoothly across diverse platforms while maintaining security, clarity, and reliability.

In practice, Simpl-Open enables systems to act as Data Providers and Data Consumers within a shared ecosystem. A Data Provider makes information accessible in a standardised format, while a Data Consumer retrieves and uses that information to power applications, automate processes, or inform decision-making. Together, these roles support a more connected, modular, and scalable digital environment where services can interoperate with minimal friction.

⁴ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0>

⁵ <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/>

⁶ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

⁷ <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/framework/>

4.2. Simpl Open (SMP) Agents Overview

With the dataspace onboarded, the next step is to ensure smooth and secure access to their resources. This role is handled by the **Simpl-Open Agents**, which sit between the individual dataspace and the interoperability framework. The agents understand the local rules and technical details of each data source but present them outwardly in a standardised way so the rest of the system can interact with them consistently.

Access is managed according to the policies of the data source. For openly available resources, the agent provides direct connections. For restricted resources, it handles authentication and authorisation, using established identity systems like **OIDC** or **SAML**. This approach allows us to respect dataspace-specific requirements while keeping the overall integration compatible with **Gaia-X** trust and **Sovereign-X**⁸ principles.

4.3. Data Provider & Data Consumer

A Data Provider is responsible for exposing information from internal systems or services in a clear, standardised format. By making data accessible through well-defined APIs, it ensures that other components, services, or organisations can reliably retrieve and use the information without needing bespoke integrations.

A Data Consumer retrieves, interprets, and makes use of data supplied by external systems or Data Providers. It is designed to understand standardised data formats, enabling smooth interoperability and allowing organisations to integrate external information into their own processes or applications with minimal effort.

4.4. Federated vs Open Access Mechanism

Simpl-Open is designed to operate across a wide variety of data environments, from fully open catalogues to highly controlled, trust-anchored federations. To accommodate these different contexts, it supports two complementary access mechanisms: Open Access and Federated Access. Both follow the same interoperability patterns, but differ in how identity, trust, and policy enforcement are applied.

Open access mechanism

In open access scenarios, data catalogues and resources are publicly reachable without the need for authentication. Simpl-Open Agents simply fetch metadata or content via

⁸ <https://sovereignx.com/>

standard endpoints (e.g., DCAT-AP feeds, JSON APIs, or HTTP resources). The emphasis here is on consistency and discoverability rather than security.

Open-access mode is especially suited for open data portals, research catalogues, and organisations wishing to publish metadata widely while still benefiting from Simpl-Open's normalisation, enrichment, and interoperability features. Although no authentication is required, provenance and licensing information remain essential, and these are captured and harmonised through the Interoperable Pipeline.

Federated access mechanism

Federated access is used when resources are protected and must only be accessed by authenticated and authorised actors within a trusted ecosystem. Simpl-Open adopts established identity and trust models - such as those aligned with Gaia-X - to ensure that access decisions are transparent, verifiable, and policy-driven.

In this mode, the Auth component exposes the provider's identity layer, typically through OIDC or OAuth2. It validates digitally signed tokens issued under recognised SIMPL trust anchors and applies fine-grained, consent-bound scopes. The Simpl-Open Agent relies on these verifiable claims to enforce downstream policies and to request protected datasets safely. This setup ensures data sovereignty, auditability, and compliance, while still enabling seamless interoperability between actors in the federation.

How these two mechanisms work together

Both open and federated access mechanisms follow the same overall Simpl-Open pattern - catalogue harvesting, metadata normalisation, and policy-aware access to distributions. The difference lies in the degree of control and verification applied at the access stage.

Open access prioritises accessibility and ease of integration, while federated access prioritises trust, accountability, and controlled sharing. By supporting both, Simpl-Open can bridge heterogeneous dataspace, allowing them to participate in a common interoperability layer regardless of their internal security requirements.

5. Common Middleware Platform

Simpl-Open emerged as part of the European Commission's Simpl programme, which was initiated to enable interoperable digital public services and cross-border data sharing within the EU. As datasources began to proliferate - Gaia-X, sector-specific research clouds, national catalogues, and internal enterprise ecosystems - it became clear that a common interoperability layer was needed to bridge their technical and organisational differences. Simpl-Open was introduced to fill this role, defining the shared interoperability standards required for large-scale, federated data exchange. Figure 3 shows an overview of integration between common middleware platform and data sources and CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOSC.

Figure 3 Simpl-Open as Common Middleware Platform integrating between data sources and Climate-Adaptdata4EOSC

Simpl-Open is adopted as the common middleware layer, individual dataspace no longer need to adapt to each other's internal technologies. Instead, each data source implements a Simpl-Open Agent that maps local systems to the shared model. From this point onward:

- Discovery becomes harmonised through standardised DCAT-AP metadata and CDIF enrichment.
- Access becomes uniform, whether open, federated, or policy constrained.
- Trust and identity are enforced consistently using recognised standards (OIDC, OAuth2, SAML).
- Data Providers and Consumers can interact without custom integration work.
- Compliance and auditability are improved through standard logs, verifiable tokens, and policy governance.
- The result is a federated yet interoperable ecosystem in which dataspace can cooperate, exchange data securely, and scale participation, without sacrificing their internal autonomy or sovereignty.

5.1. Authentication & Authorisation between Simpl Open (SMP) Agent & Common Middleware Platform (Simpl Open Platform)

This service performs federated enforcement for machine-to-machine exchanges. It validates issuer chains, token audiences, consent receipts, and trust registries. Successful checks mint or forward tokens used by Agents and the Interoperable Repository, thereby implementing SIMPL identity/consent/trust at infrastructure level.

In Simpl-Open, Authentication and Authorisation ensure that every interaction in the data space is secure and trustworthy. The system verifies identities and permissions for all types of participants, whether they are consuming data, providing data, offering applications, or managing infrastructure. This prevents misuse and ensures that only the right people or systems can access the right resources.

Simpl-Open uses a two-tier identity model (Tier-1 and Tier-2) to manage authentication effectively across different situations. Tier-1 focuses on users inside an organisation. When someone wants to use their organisation's Simpl-Open Agent, they log in through the identity system that their organisation already uses, such as EU Login, eID or an OpenID Connect provider. This tier confirms who the user is and lets the organisation assign roles so users can act on behalf of the organisation when interacting with the data space.

Tier-2 handles authentication between different organisations. Here, trust is established directly between the agents representing each participant in the data space. This is done using X.509 certificates, cryptographic keys, and identity credentials issued by the Governance Authority. These elements allow each agent to prove its identity and provide the attributes required to check whether access should be granted. All communication

between agents is secured through mutual TLS, which ensures both sides are authenticated and their connection is protected.

Through this two-tier structure, Simpl-Open supports secure authentication both for users within an organisation and for automated interactions between participants across the wider data space.

5.2. Federated Access Catalogue

A federation-wide DCAT-AP aggregation that supports cross-provider discovery. It exposes search and harvesting interfaces consumed by Agents and by the Interoperable Pipeline. Catalogue entries propagate into FAIRification as “metadata seeds”, later reconciled with semantic artefacts under CDIF Discovery.

The Federated Catalogue in Simpl-Open is provided through the XFSC Federated Catalogue, which offers a discovery capability for looking up Self-Descriptions of Data, Application, and Infrastructure service offerings. It validates Self-Descriptions when they are published and supports searching through a federated view of these resources. The catalogue is operated at the Governance Authority, while each provider maintains an organisational credential manager to store and sign its own Self-Descriptions and to support their verification and retrieval. Through this setup, participants rely on a common mechanism for publishing and discovering service offerings, ensuring that Self-Descriptions are consistently validated and accessible within the Simpl-Open data space.

5.3. Metadata Flow

In the Simpl-Open architecture, metadata enters the system from the original data sources and is first collected as descriptive information about the resource. This incoming metadata is forwarded to the FAIRification pipeline, where it is transformed, enriched, and aligned with the required standards and semantic models. As part of this process, the metadata may also be matched with Self-Descriptions and identity attributes already registered in the data space. The FAIRified output becomes the harmonised and standardised metadata used for discovery, policy evaluation, and downstream CDIF processes, ensuring that resources can be consistently interpreted and reused across participants.

6. FAIRification Pipeline & Interoperability

To enable interoperability in the access, sharing, integration and reuse of climate data, it is necessary to provide a toolkit comprised of components that can facilitate these core functions. The development of those components must also be informed by legal, organisational and technical considerations, and thus requires a collaborative approach across relevant WPs (WP2, WP3 and WP4).

This work is undertaken across Task 2.2, building upon the work of Tasks 2.1 and T1.4, capturing requirements and documenting necessary files/format considerations (GeoTIFF, NetCDF, CSV, etc.).

As part of this work, the minimal requirements that the metadata must meet (mandatory elements) will need to be identified. Those metadata will (also) be extracted into a structured representation (e.g. RO-Crate), which will track the various stages of data and metadata flow during the processing of that data, and importantly also allow traceback to source and provenance tracking.

These toolkit components, some of which will be 'templates' which will allow the data to be uploaded into a database, and additional components will enable the conversion of data generated in one format, to be extracted in an alternative form(at), using mapping components. This conceptual toolkit and its components are show in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4 FAIRification pipeline and Toolkit components

6.1. FAIRification Template

At a dedicated meeting⁹, hosted by UNIMAN, WPs 1-4 met to discuss the Toolkit and templates. As described above, the FAIRification template is one of a few components that comprise the overall toolkit, and indeed it could be imagined that ‘template’ itself could represent a diverse set of types of templates, many of which could or will be required.

Inspired by the work of the FAIRplus project, which generated a diverse set of templates¹⁰, and by FAIR-IMPACT¹¹, which generated ‘mapping’ related templates, we may decide to implement some of the following types:

- Categorisation template

Figure 5 Categorisation template

This template (FAIRplus) lists the stages in a typical data FAIRification, with sub-stages listed for each step.

⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1nTydls-FptXhsxLuM0br5h1GMiZcle2DRYvJE2qUWu4/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.l3gw8e615itc>

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/7501964>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15310718>

- FAIR status template

Figure 6 FAIR status template

This template style allows the tracking of progress in a semi-standard way and is more suited to visualising progress towards a desired FAIR state.

- Mapping stage template (FAIR-IMPACT)

Figure 7 Mapping stage template (FAIR-IMPACT)

This template depicts the stages in a typical mapping and its subsequent review

- Guided user centric template (FAIR-IMPACT)

1	Context	Are there existing mappings for this use case or similar?	<input type="text"/>	link (optional)	use case link
5	Context	If so, why are they unsuitable?	text		documented use case link
3	Nature	Is it a one-off solution or will it be maintained?	<input type="text"/>		Protocol
7	Nature	If applicable, where will the solution be maintained	<input type="text"/>	hosting resource link	Protocol
3	Nature	Have you decided on a license?	<input type="text"/>	link	Protocol
3	Nature	How will you share the protocol	<input type="text"/>	link	Protocol
0	Sustainability	If applicable, how will you incorporate feedback, refine & update	text or n/a		Protocol
1	Nature	Does the mapping involve any standard or established vocabulary as source?	<input type="text"/>	vocabulary link	Protocol
2	Nature	Does the mapping involve any standard or established vocabulary as target?	<input type="text"/>	vocabulary link	Protocol
3	Scope	What will the solution look like?	<input type="text"/>		Protocol
4	Scope	What are the relationships between source and target terms? (semantic terms to be used)	<input type="text"/>	terms link	Protocol
5	Scope	Will the mapping be manual or automated?	<input type="text"/>		Protocol
6	Scope	identified source	URI		Protocol
7	Scope	Source - identify the concepts to be mapped	text or link(s)		Protocol
8	Scope	identified target	URI		Protocol
9	Scope	Target - identify the concepts to be mapped	text or link(s)		Protocol
n					

Figure 8 Guided user centric template (FAIR-IMPACT)

This template is focused on gathering user input, providing guidance on what specific information is required, providing guidance on how to complete each section, and describing where that information is used subsequently.

Discussions are ongoing to define the relationship of templates and toolkit components, to enable complete connection between the various sources and formats, as well as the requirements across use cases, and data/source mapping. One solution is to aim towards an overarching RO-Crate ‘interconversion’ structure, to which components could be plugged, and against which components could be developed. Discussions are also needed for ‘who’ templates should be aimed at, as well as the granularity at which they should be targeted (e.g., specific task per format, and/or overall process). As described above, it is likely that several templates will be required, as well as of different types, and targeting different tasks/roles.

6.2. Interoperability Framework (IF) Strategies

6.2.1. Technical Interoperability Framework

In this deliverable, **Technical IF** refers to the basic “if-then” conditions that define how a system, service, or node must behave **if it wants to work smoothly within the Climate-Adapt4EOSC ecosystem**. These conditions describe what technical capabilities are required for interoperability, security, and consistent user experience. In simple terms, *if* a component wants to join the wider EOSC or Simpl-Open environment, *then* it needs to follow a small set of agreed rules. For example, **if** a Node wants to enable federated login, **it must** use the common identity and authentication standards (e.g., OIDC/OAuth2). **If** a service wants to share data, **it must** publish a valid Self-Description so others can understand and

use it. **If** workflows run across nodes, **they must** use the common token validation and policy mechanisms to keep everything secure. These Technical IFs help ensure that different data sources can still connect, exchange information, and work together reliably. They provide a simple baseline that every participant needs to follow so the whole federation remains coherent and easy to use.

6.2.2. Semantic Interoperability Framework

The semantic interoperability framework will be composed of the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC ontology, an intermediate schema, and an ontology-based data access (OBDA) tool, e.g., Ontop¹². The ontology will capture the concepts, object properties, and datatype properties required to represent different facets of climate change adaptation, including climate change effects, impacts, risks, and adaptation measures, as well as location, population, and vulnerability. The intermediate schema will host source data in Postgres database tables with the PostGIS extension enabled. Geocoordinates available in source CSV, Shapefile, and raster datasets will be converted into geometry objects. An OBDA mapping file will be created to link the ontology, published in a publicly accessible repository, with the data stored in the intermediate schema. The OBDA tool will operate on the mappings, ontology, and intermediate schema to enable users to perform SPARQL queries that retrieve ontology-based standardised data. A SPARQL endpoint will be exposed to fulfil the input data requirements of Climate-Adapt4EOOSC services. This standardised, ontology-driven data will be suitable for consumption by the technical interoperability framework to meet the file-format-specific requirements of downstream services (e.g., GeoTIFF or GeoJSON).

6.2.3. Legal Interoperability Framework

The legal interoperability framework approach consists of two components:

- Deploying and further developing semantic frameworks that describe coherently legal constraints related to the use of data and tools, leveraging and engaging with developments related to the CDIF Data Access profile¹³, Data Use Ontology¹⁴, and Data Privacy Vocabulary¹⁵. The results of this activity are captured as implementation guidelines and metadata models.
- Collecting and analysing the use cases in terms of legally enforceable restrictions related to data use (e.g. due to concerns related to privacy, security or contractual arrangements). The results of this activity are different decision support tools

¹² <https://ontop-vkg.org/>

¹³ https://cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/data_access/intro.html

¹⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/data-use-ontology-duo/>

(process descriptions, checklists or other types of analysis frameworks).

The deliverable D3.1 will include additional background of this activity.

6.2.4. Organisational Interoperability Framework

Similar to Legal IF, the organisational interoperability framework consists of semantic artefacts and process descriptions and guidelines:

- The organisational agreements related to resource integration (including cross-sectoral/organisational scenarios) will be described in a machine-actionable manner. The inputs include SLAs/MoUs/tacit agreements used in the use case pilots as well as the resource onboarding approaches in the emerging federated EOOSC infrastructure and links with the other Common European Data Spaces.
- Support material (checklists, decision support tools) for managing other inter-organisational factors influencing the efficiency, reliability and resiliency of the cross-organisational workflows.

When possible, Legal and Organisational IF will use common approaches to presenting the solutions, ideally as an integrated package. The deliverable D3.1 will contain additional background related to organisational interoperability.

6.2.5. Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework

The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) The Cross Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (<https://cdif.codata.org>) is a set of practical, implementation-level principles designed to improve data management practices within any community and lower the barriers to cross-domain data reuse. Initially produced by the EC-funded WorldFAIR project, CDIF is now an international, discipline-agnostic and extensible framework for implementing FAIR and achieving interoperability. It comprises a set of profiles, guidelines and worked examples developed to address clearly defined functional requirements of FAIR integration.

CDIF offers standards and methodologies to enable interoperability and reusability of data across diverse domains. CDIF is built around five core profiles that address the essential functions for implementing cross-domain FAIR principles. The current profiles cover:

- **Discovery:** Provides a content model with required, recommended and optional items, including a notable recommendation to include descriptions of the variable measured in the Discovery metadata; mappings between two widely used content standards (Schema.org and DCAT) and a practical guide to using a JSON-LD serialisation.
- **Data description:** comprises two important components, notably the variable

cascade to associate the variable measured with its abstract definition, and descriptions of data structure to assist with the decomposition and recomposition of datasets.

- **Controlled vocabularies/FAIR vocabularies:** Offers a basic guide to good practice to describe controlled vocabularies/FAIR vocabularies using SKOS.
- **Access:** Provides a guide to using ODRL as the basis for 'a more structured and standardised, machine-actionable approach' to rights management.
- **Universals:** Offers an introduction to good practice in describing location, time and units of measurement.

CDIF is not the finished product. Currently, the CDIF profiles are presented through the CDIF Book at <https://cdif.codata.org>. As part of the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC project, work is underway to create a more formal production site with complete field-level documentation for the Discovery, Data Description and FAIR Terminologies profiles. Driven by a UML model, this service will provide the authoritative single source of truth for both human-readable field-level documentation and the automatic generation of machine-readable encodings such as JSON-LD contexts, JSON Schema, and SHACL shapes, so that all semantics are consistently derived from one maintained model. This will better enable implementation of CDIF recommendations.

In parallel, further work is going on to extend CDIF, adding profiles on Semantic Mapping and on Provenance, while extending and refining the profile on Access. These topics were the focus of a recent CODATA-DDI Dagstuhl Workshop '[The Provenance Chain: Connecting and Reusing Data, Models, and Experiments](#)'¹⁶, which was highly relevant to the work of Climate-Adapt4EOOSC.

All the CDIF profiles are important to the work of Climate-Adapt4EOOSC. Mapping of existing metadata and semantics to the CDIF Discovery and Data Description Profiles will be an important step when preparing to integrate data in all three Use Cases. That integration will hinge on variable descriptions (CDIF Data Description using DDI-CDI, and also I-ADOPT); machine-readable, standards-based and reusable descriptions of Semantic Mappings; as well as good practice in describing time and space (Universals). A contribution of the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC project will be to refine and improve the CDIF Profile on Universals.

The integration pipeline will provide an opportunity to test and refine emerging CDIF recommendations on Provenance and to make sure these align with the use of the Common Workflow Language. Similarly, Climate-Adapt4EOOSC will make a considerable contribution to the further development and extension of the Access profile, providing

¹⁶<https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/DDI4/pages/3837133351/2025+The+Provenance+Chain+Connecting+and+Reusing+Data+Models+and+Experiments>

concrete examples of restrictions and obligation that need to be encoded to achieve Legal and Organisational Interoperability.

Finally, the alignment of CDIF and RO-Crate, with CDIF providing a profile of metadata and semantics that can be packaged in a particular ‘type’ of RO-Crate will be a significant contribution to practices around FAIRification and the creation of FAIR Digital Objects (based on RO-Crates).

Figure 9 FAIRification workflow in CA4EOOSC, showing key use of CDIF Profiles

7. Intermediate Schema

The intermediate schema serves as the central data layer that hosts heterogeneous climate-related datasets to be reconciled with the semantic layer defined by the Climate-Adapt4EOSC ontology. Its primary role is to provide a harmonised and query-efficient representation of diverse geospatial and tabular data, supporting ontology-based data access (OBDA) and enabling high-performance SPARQL querying. The schema is implemented in a Postgres database with the PostGIS extension enabled to ensure that both vector and raster geospatial information can be stored, indexed, and processed effectively. Through the architectural separation of data from the ontology, the semantic interoperability framework offers scalability, maintainability, and flexibility - allowing dataset evolution and ontology modification or extension to be accommodated simply by updating the OBDA mappings.

7.1. Data Transformation and Storage

Input source files from different formats, such as CSV, Shapefile, and raster, will be processed for transformation into a queryable format. Geocoordinates available in CSV and vector datasets will be converted into PostGIS geometry objects (e.g., POINT, LINESTRING, and POLYGON) to enable spatial indexing for efficient query execution, and compatibility with geospatial SPARQL functions. Different attributes/variables represented in raster data as bands will be extracted from the raster database tables. Raster bands appearing in a single file - typically representing variables such as land surface temperature, precipitation, vegetation index, and population density - will be processed, with each band stored in a separate column within a database table. This approach mitigates performance bottlenecks that can arise when executing SPARQL queries across large raster layers. These transformed and harmonised datasets will be stored in the intermediate schema, where they can be accessed through OBDA mappings that link database fields to ontology concepts and properties.

8. CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC

8.1. Query Service

The Query Service in CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC project enables users and system components to discover and access datasets, metadata, and services across connected data spaces in a unified way. It operates through the Simpl-Open Agent, which acts as the local gateway on each participant node and ensures that all queries follow the applicable access rules and policies.

For Open Access resources, the Query Service allows users to search and explore metadata and FAIRified outputs without authentication, supporting openness and discoverability. For resources requiring Federated Access, queries are evaluated based on user identity and attributes provided through the EOOSC AAI infrastructure, ensuring that only authorised users can access restricted information.

The Query Service is integrated into the CA4EOOSC user dashboard, helping researchers easily find relevant climate data and select inputs for FAIRification workflows in a secure and interoperable manner.

8.1.1. Simpl Open (SMP) Agent Functionality

In the Simpl-Open architecture, the Simpl-Open Agent is the main piece of software installed on every participant node. It works as the local gateway that allows the node to communicate safely with others in the data space. The agent connects the different actors in the network and makes it possible for them to share data, applications, and infrastructure. It offers the common services needed to run a data space and does not depend on the rules or details of any specific data space, so extra services can be added when needed.

The agent represents the participant's node and handles all communication with other agents. Whenever a user or an internal system performs an action, it goes through the local agent, which then talks to the provider, consumer, or governance components. Through this, the agent manages identity checks, access control, and the application of rules and policies.

Depending on the role of the participant (Consumer, Data Provider, Infrastructure Provider, or Governance Authority), the Simpl-Open Agent brings together several functions such as onboarding, authentication, metadata handling, publishing resources, searching and discovering services, negotiating contracts, provisioning infrastructure, and managing logs and monitoring. All these functions help participants offer resources, use resources from

others, check permissions, sign and manage contracts, handle credentials, and communicate securely with other agents in the data space.

8.2. User Access

CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC will adopt both Open Access and Federated Access to support different levels of data availability and user needs. Open Access will be used for non-sensitive datasets, public FAIR Digital Climate Objects, and general metadata that can be accessed without authentication. This approach supports broad reuse and aligns with the project's commitment to open climate information.

Federated Access will be applied when datasets or services require controlled permissions, licensing checks, or policy-based restrictions. Users will authenticate through EOOSC AAI or their institutional identity, and access rights will be evaluated using CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC's Policy Engine. This enables secure and traceable access to sensitive or restricted climate data and services.

In the C2IMPRESS project, similar principle was followed but relied mainly on Open Access. Copernicus Open Access was one of our key data sources, where only minimal authorisation was needed to retrieve Earth observation datasets.

8.3. FAIR Publisher Service

8.3.1. Simpl Open (SMP) Agent as Consumer

When acting as a Consumer, the Simpl Open (SMP) Agent represents the participant node in accessing resources published in the Dataspace. The process begins when the Agent searches the Dataspace Catalogue and selects a dataset, application, or infrastructure offering. The Agent then triggers the contract negotiation process through the Contract Negotiation Adapter, which communicates with the Provider's Connector to validate the requested asset and retrieve usage and access policies.

Once the Consumer agrees to these terms, a formal usage contract is negotiated and finalised between both connectors. After the contract is in place, the Simpl Open (SMP) Agent manages the technical consumption: either receiving access details for deployed infrastructure or initiating a data transfer based on the agreed contract. In this role, the Simpl Open (SMP) Agent ensures that all Consumer actions - search, negotiation, policy compliance, and resource usage - follow the SIMPL-Open governance and Dataspace Protocol requirements.

9. CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOSC

9.1. Just Climate Urban Resilience Service (Just-CURS)

The use case develops an Urban Digital Climate Twin that integrates environmental, climatic, socio-economic, and geospatial data with analytical services and community input. Through a combination of climate profiling, heatwave risk assessment, summer energy poverty analysis, carbon footprint estimation, and community resilience indicators, the Digital Twin aims to support evidence-based decision-making. The platform enables the exploration of “what-if” adaptation scenarios, such as nature-based solutions and targeted cooling interventions, with a focus on reducing heat-related risks and improving resilience for vulnerable populations.

Figure 10 Just Climate Urban Resilience Service (Just-CURS)

9.1.1. High-Level System Architecture

The Digital Twin architecture for the Aigaleo (AGL) region is designed as a modular, service-oriented platform that integrates heterogeneous analytical services, geospatial repositories, serving also as a unified decision-support environment. The system aims to support urban climate adaptation, resilience assessment, and scenario exploration by combining analytical outputs with interactive geospatial visualization.

Figure 11 High-level architecture of the Climate-Adapt4EOSC Digital Twin

The system integrates presentation, application, data, and EOSC backbone layers to support climate adaptation services. Datasets are processed through FAIRification and interoperability tools and services are exposed through REST APIs and accessed via the Digital Twin Interface, which is integrated with EOSC authentication, cloud infrastructure, and federated data services.

At the core of the architecture lies the Digital Twin Interface, which acts as the central access and interaction point for all user interactions, service requests, and visualization workflows. All service access, map composition, and report delivery will be mediated through this interface, enabling a unified and consistent user experience. The proposed architecture is designed as a layered Digital Twin ecosystem, integrating domain-specific analytical services, and federated data resources under a common interaction model. The system is envisioned to operate within the EOSC Backbone, leveraging its authentication, cloud infrastructure, FAIR data services, and federation capabilities. The system is logically decomposed into the following layers:

- EOSC Backbone
- Presentation & Interaction Layer

- Application & Analytics Layer
- Data Integration Layer

The Digital Twin Interface will serve as the main point of contact for user access, which will be mediated through the EOSC ecosystem. Authentication and authorization are expected to be provided via EOSC AAI services, while the Digital Twin Interface will progressively assume responsibility for request routing, response aggregation, and service orchestration. As the platform develops, it is anticipated that this common interface will offer map visualization, layer creation, and report delivery, allowing for a consistent user experience across services and lowering client-side complexity.

9.1.2. Data Architecture and Federation Model

The Digital Twin adopts a **federated data architecture**, aligned with EOSC principles, where data ownership, storage, and lifecycle management remain within the respective service domains. At the current stage, databases will be operated independently, while future interoperability options may be explored as the platform evolves.

Distributed Data Stores

- The **NCSR** database is planned as the primary repository for outputs generated by the hosted analytical services. It is intended to store both spatial and non-spatial datasets, including climate profile indicators, heatwave risk metrics, energy poverty indicators, scenario-based analytical results, and additional datasets that will be formally described in the Services and Application Layer. The database will be implemented using PostgreSQL/PostGIS, supporting combined management of tabular indicators and geospatial data. Analytical outputs are expected to be precomputed and stored for efficient reuse.
- The **GIS** database¹⁷ hosts the authoritative base geographical layers for the AGL region, such as administrative boundaries, road networks, land use, and public spaces. It is optimised for spatial queries and map tile generation.
- The **CoolScape** database is intended to store outputs generated by the CoolScape scenario-based modelling workflows. It includes spatial and non-spatial datasets describing the cooling potential of urban and neighbourhood-scale interventions, such as estimated air temperature reductions and thermal comfort indicators (e.g. PET¹⁸, UTCI¹⁹) under different adaptation scenarios and atmospheric conditions. The database is designed to support structured access to scenario outputs for

¹⁷ <https://ydom.egaleo.gr/geopyli/episkeftheite-ti-geopyli/>

¹⁸ Höpfe, P. The physiological equivalent temperature – a universal index for the biometeorological assessment of the thermal environment. *Int J Biometeorol* **43**, 71–75 (1999). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004840050118>

¹⁹ Jendritzky, G., de Dear, R. & Havenith, G. UTCI—Why another thermal index?. *Int J Biometeorol* **56**, 421–428 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-011-0513-7>

visualization and analysis through the Digital Twin Interface. The databases managed exclusively by the CoolScape service.

9.1.3. Presentation Layer

The Digital Twin Interface is envisioned as a unified web-based entry point for accessing the Digital Twin services. Users will be able to access maps, indicators, and reports via a single interface thanks to its consistent interaction layer. EOOSC AAI is anticipated to manage authentication and authorization, enabling safe access and single sign-on as needed. In its initial design, the interface will receive user requests, route them to the appropriate backend services, and aggregate responses into coherent visual outputs.

9.1.4. Application and Analytics Layer

The Application & Analytics Layer contains the domain-specific analytical services. These components are currently conceptualised as scripts or analytical pipelines and are planned to be progressively exposed as RESTful APIs.

Each service focuses on a specific thematic domain and is expected to:

- Execute analytical workflows
- Generate geospatial outputs (map layers)
- Produce tabular or document-based reports

Planned services include:

- **Climate Profile**
- **Heatwave Risk**
- **Summer Energy Poverty**
- **Carbon Footprint**
- **Citizen Engagement**
- **CoolScape**
- **GIS**
- **Community Assessment**

The architecture allows services to evolve independently in complexity and computational demand.

1. Climate Profile Service

The Climate Profile Service is planned to provide a structured climatic baseline and future projections for the regions of the case studies. The service will consolidate climate

simulation outputs into reusable datasets and reports suitable for both map-based visualization and offline analysis.

Design and Implementation

This service is designed as a data-processing pipeline that will be progressively encapsulated into a callable service. Existing analysis scripts (Python/R) will be adapted to operate as backend workflows, triggered either on demand or at scheduled intervals.

The service will ingest regional climate datasets (e.g., EURO-CORDEX²⁰) and observational references, compute standard climate indices, and store outputs in tabular format. These outputs will then be exposed through planned API endpoints for dataset download and report creation or layers that can be projected on the map.

Planned Outputs

- CSV datasets of climate variables and indices
- Summary figures and static visualizations
- Automatically generated climate profile reports

2. Summer Energy Poverty Assessment

The Summer Energy Poverty Assessment is planned as an analytical service within the Digital Twin framework, aiming to identify population groups and urban areas that are vulnerable to inadequate cooling during summer heat conditions. The service is designed to integrate climatic stress indicators with socio-economic and housing-related data to support targeted adaptation and policy planning.

Design and Implementation

The assessment will be implemented as a modular analytical workflow. Results are intended to be pre-computed and stored in the NCSR database, enabling efficient reuse and visualization through the DT Interface. The service is designed to operate independently from other analytical components, while remaining interoperable through standardized APIs. Its outputs may be visualized as thematic map layers within the GIS environment and made available as downloadable datasets and reports, depending on access policies.

Figure 12 Climate Profile Service

²⁰ <https://www.euro-cordex.net/>

Planned Outputs

The planned outputs of the Summer Energy Poverty Assessment include:

- Spatial indicators identifying areas with elevated summer energy poverty risk
- Aggregated indices describing vulnerability at block or municipal scale
- Geospatial layers suitable for map-based visualization within the Digital Twin
- Tabular outputs and summary reports (pdf) to support decision-making and policy design

These outputs are intended to support evidence-based interventions, such as targeted cooling measures and social support actions, while allowing flexibility for future methodological refinement and data integration.

3. Heatwave Risk Assessment Service

The Heatwave Risk Service is designed to assess spatial heat exposure and population vulnerability at multiple spatial scales, with an emphasis on block-level urban analysis

Design and Implementation

Developed in R and Python, the service uses multi-source data: Landsat 8/9 LST, WorldPop²¹ population density, and CORDEX-based heatwave indices (EHF, HI, WBGT). The engine computes normalized risk indices per urban block and stores them in a PostGIS database.

Planned Outputs

Map layers (hw_risk_block), downloadable shapefiles and CSV summaries via the Twin Core API.

4. Carbon Footprint

Calculates greenhouse gas emissions for municipal sectors (buildings, transport, waste) within the city boundaries.

Planned Outputs

²¹ Tatem, A. WorldPop, open data for spatial demography. *Sci Data* **4**, 170004 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.4>

CO₂-equivalent emission maps per sector, tabular summaries, and official reports for city-wide carbon accounting.

5. Citizen Engagement

Citizen input is gathered through participatory workshops and web forms, stored as point/polygon features, and reviewed before publication. Each Natural Based Solutions (NBS) proposal is categorized (e.g., shading, vegetation, water retention) and visualized as an interactive layer in the Digital Twin map. The data are queryable by geometry, type, or project ID through a REST API.

6. CoolScape Service

The CoolScape service is designed to produce scenario-based analytical outputs describing the cooling potential of urban and neighborhood-scale interventions. Planned outputs include spatial layers (e.g. temperature reduction maps, thermal comfort indicators) and aggregated indicators summarising intervention effectiveness under different climatic conditions. These outputs will be stored in the CoolScape/Coolspace database and exposed through standard APIs, enabling visualization, comparison, and reporting through the Digital Twin Interface.

7. Community Resilience Assessment

Implemented as a web-based scoring system that aggregates 41 quantitative and qualitative indicators related to infrastructure, demographics, governance, and environment. Users (experts or policymakers) can apply weights interactively through a web UI built in React + FastAPI backend. Data are exported as CSV while the adaptation measures are exported in PDF reports. The service supports versioned scenarios, enabling “what-if” evaluations of policy interventions.

9.1.5. EOSC Backbone

Instead of hosting domain logic, it is meant to facilitate data persistence, scalable execution, secure access, and service interoperability.

Key functions foreseen in this layer include:

- **Federated Authentication and Authorization**, relying on EOSC AAI to support single sign-on and controlled access to services and datasets.
- **Cloud and Compute Infrastructure**, enabling deployment and execution of analytical services and workflows, with the ability to scale as computational

demands increase.

- **Federated Storage and Data Access**, supporting persistent storage of datasets and analytical outputs in accordance with FAIR principles.
- **Interoperability and Federation Support**, enabling integration with external EOOSC services, data hubs, and registries.

9.1.6. Adapters

Adapters will encapsulate the complexity of interacting with heterogeneous data sources and formats, including environmental, climate, socio-economic, and geospatial datasets. Planned ETL processes include:

- **Extraction** of data from external providers, EOOSC services, and local sources.
- **Transformation and Harmonisation**, including format conversion, spatial and temporal alignment, metadata enrichment, and quality checks.
- **FAIRification**, ensuring datasets are accompanied by appropriate metadata, standardised schemas, and persistent identifiers where applicable.
- **Loading** of processed datasets into the corresponding databases (NCSR, GIS, CoolScape), following service-specific data models.

Adapters are designed to be reusable and loosely coupled, supporting both batch and incremental data flows. This approach allows analytical services to remain focused on domain logic, while data interoperability, provenance, and compliance with FAIR principles are handled consistently across the platform.

9.2. OPENHIDRA

OPENHIDRA is proposed as a CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOOSC by integrating the coastal and lagoon circulation simulations from OPENCoastS with the management and early-warning capabilities of HIDRALERTA. The service will provide a unified platform that can operate either in planning mode (supporting climate-change scenarios and other what-if analyses) or in an operational early-warning mode for anticipated hazard prediction.

OPENHIDRA aims to support the assessment and management of port, coastal and estuarine risks, including flooding, sea-level rise, erosion, and disruptions to port activities. It offers site-specific hydrodynamic simulations and real-time forecasting tools that help users understand local coastal dynamics and the interactions between natural processes and human activities. The integration within EOOSC facilitates data exchange, reproducibility, and wider accessibility for researchers, decision-makers, and coastal and port managers.

9.2.1. High-Level System Architecture

The OPENHIDRA architecture aims to integrate two existing systems, OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA, within the EOOSC ecosystem, forming an integrated service for port, coastal and estuarine forecasting and climate-adaptation analysis. The system relies on EOOSC services for authentication, storage, persistent identifiers, and workload orchestration.

Figure 13 OPENHIDRA Architecture

OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA maintain their own web frontend and backend (including spatial database and computing nodes) and run on cloud resources hosted at CNCA (Portuguese National Center for Advanced Computing) and IFCA Scientific Cloud Infrastructure. For larger computational demands, the system intends to extend to batch clusters at CNCA, IFCA, and other sites, where jobs are submitted for parallel execution (via the EGI Dirac Workload manager). All user access and workflow initiation will be routed through the EOOSC Marketplace and authenticated via EGI Check-in, while persistent datasets will be stored in EUDAT's B2SAFE infrastructure.

9.2.2. Data Architecture and Federation Model

OPENHIDRA adopts a federated data architecture consistent with EOOSC principles. OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA each manage their own PostGIS spatial databases and rely on their respective NextCloud instances for file storage and metadata handling. Simulation results, early-warning datasets, and configuration files can be exchanged through EOOSC storage, which provides long-term persistence and discoverability. Authentication and authorisation are handled through EOOSC AAI (EGI Check-In Authentication), allowing users and services across institutions to access shared resources while maintaining local autonomy. This federation model ensures that the two systems remain independently operable but fully interoperable when running under the integrated OPENHIDRA service.

9.2.3. Data-Adapters

The OPENHIDRA architecture, and its services, will use a set of data-adapter components that connect heterogeneous data sources, modelling systems, and EOOSC services. Although not explicitly depicted in the architectural diagram (Figure 13), these adapters are essential to enable access to external data and communication between the services, OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA. Data adapters will be used to streamline and standardise the complex process of acquiring, transforming, and preparing external datasets for simulation, encapsulating all steps from authentication to conversion into model-ready schemes, as well as transforming model outputs to standardised formats.

Within OPENCoastS, the existing backend already implements a set of adapters, located in the forcings module, responsible for acquiring, transforming, and validating environmental data from external providers, such as Copernicus Marine, ECMWF, NOAA, Meteo-France, Meteo-Galicia, IPMA atmospheric and oceanographic products, and national hydrological services. They normalise temporal resolutions, spatial grids, coordinate systems, metadata conventions, and variable naming schemes into a unified internal representation used as input by simulation models, such as SCHISM, and other coastal/estuarine simulation engines deployed by OPENCoastS. The same adapters also perform downstream translation by transforming model outputs into service-compatible formats (e.g., NetCDF). Similar adapters will be implemented in HIDRALERTA to generate the system forcings

required for the downstream hazard-warning chain (e.g., hazard-specific maps and warning), ensuring that outputs conform to the fixed templates used by the operational dashboards and alerting services.

9.2.4. Application Layer

The application layer is composed by the operational services that transform input datasets into actionable forecasts or climate change scenario simulations within both OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA. While the two systems address different hazard domains, coastal and estuarine hydrodynamics in OPENCoastS and coastal/port flood early warning and ship safety in HIDRALERTA, their backend architectures follow a similar execution model built on orchestrated simulation workflows, configurable model pipelines, and managed result dissemination.

In OPENCoastS, the backend implements the full workflow lifecycle: it assembles the model configuration from project metadata and related forcings, generates run directories for models such as SCHISM, WaveWatchIII, or SWAN, and submits jobs to the available execution environment (i.e., local HPC clusters, EOOSC-managed resources, or cloud workers). The platform manages job scheduling, monitors execution, and executes post-processing tasks to convert outputs into service endpoints (NetCDF for ncWMS layers, timeseries exports, scenario files, etc.). These processes rely on worker nodes that execute model runs in parallel while maintaining provenances for all produced artefacts.

In HIDRALERTA, the application layer is centred on continuous data ingestion and real-time forecasting logic. Its backend integrates sensor data streams, wave overtopping modelling, ship safety modelling, and threshold-based impact modules. Worker processes run recurrent forecasting cycles, generating hazard-specific maps, time series, hazard indicators, and impact classifications) to support early-warning decision rules. As with OPENCoastS, post-processing routines will ensure that outputs conform to predefined templates for dashboards, alerting interfaces, and downstream municipal systems.

Under the OPENHIDRA architecture, the two application domains will operate cohesively. Outputs produced by OPENCoastS (e.g., coastal water levels and velocities, surge components, boundary conditions) can feed HIDRALERTA simulations, forecasts and scenarios, while HIDRALERTA's real-time impact outputs can be exposed as additional service products within the broader coastal, port, and estuarine monitoring ecosystem. The application layer integrates EOOSC Workload Orchestrator capabilities by allowing simulations and forecasting jobs to be distributed across heterogeneous execution environments, local HPC, EOOSC cloud, or hybrid infrastructures, using unified submission and monitoring procedures inherited from WIFF, the Water Information Forecast Framework developed in LNEC. This creates a consistent operational backbone where both services can execute jointly, share data where and when required, and expose results to external consumers through harmonised APIs and persistent identifiers.

9.2.5. Presentation Layer

Figure 14 OPENHIDRA Portal

OPENHIDRA will include a unified web portal with single sign-on (SSO) based on EGI Authentication, ensuring seamless and secure access for all users for OPENHIDRA's services. Through this central entry point, users will be able to navigate directly to the OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA frontends, while also benefiting from an integrated output viewer capable of displaying results from both services.

OPENCoastS and HIDRALERTA each have a dedicated web-based configuration assistant that guides users through the setup and management of their systems and deployments. They also include portals for handling user accounts, project settings, and deployments configurations, as well as interactive web map visualization tools designed to present geospatial information. The OPENCoastS interface allows users to design and manage model simulations, including the selection of domains, boundary conditions, forcing data, and deployment parameters. It supports the exploration of simulation outputs through time series, statistics, and spatial visualization provided by ncWMS map-based services, enabling analysis of hydrodynamic conditions. Further, HIDRALERTA interface offer a web configuration assistant to setup wave forecasts, water-level predictions, overtopping estimations, and inundation modelling, enabling operational coastal-hazard monitoring. Together, the two systems maintain their specialized roles and interfaces but can draw on shared storage, common datasets, and unified authentication workflows when operating within the OPENHIDRA framework.

9.3. 3SES - Shrink-Swell from Space2Earth Service

The **Shrink-Swell from Space2Earth Service (3SES)** service (UC3) represents a critical climate adaptation tool aimed at allowing users, particularly the general public, professionals, and institutions, to understand the current and future risk linked to clay shrinkage and swelling phenomena. The risk arises from changes in soil volume due to moisture fluctuations in high water retention clay minerals, leading to structural damage and significant financial consequences. The service is designed to provide **static risk mapping** (exposure) and a **dynamic alert system**. The initial application area is Metropolitan France, but lessons learned will enable replication across the European territory. 3SES will offer a **free-of-charge** service to inform citizens and a **chargeable service function** for professionals requiring higher levels of detail and dynamic risk assessment.

9.3.1. High-Level System Architecture

At a high level, the 3SES web service follows a **three-tier web architecture**:

- A **presentation layer** implemented using **Next.js**, this layer manages the web user interface (UI), the **Interactive Map Dashboard**, and map visualization. It handles user interaction and the display of results, including risk layer overlays and contextual information.
- An **application layer** implemented using **FastAPI** (Python), this layer constitutes the service core. It hosts all business logic, risk querying services, scenario analysis endpoints, and integration with the processing components.
- A **data and integration layer**: This foundational layer manages data access. It integrates external data sources via **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOsc** and hosts the internal data repository, referred to as the 3SES Data Lake.

User interaction flows from the browser to the Next.js frontend, then to the FastAPI backend, and finally to the data and integration components. Responses (such as risk maps, indicators or reports) follow the reverse direction to be visualised on the map or presented as numerical outputs.

Figure 15 3SES System Architecture Overview

9.3.2. Data Architecture and Federation Model

3SES operates as a **Data Consumer** service within the project ecosystem and is fundamentally dependent on the shared CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC component for all standardized data inputs.

1. **Federated Data Access:** 3SES relies on **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC** to retrieve FAIR-compliant data, including climate projections (DRIAS, TRACC, CMIP6), geological maps (BRGM), soil moisture (Copernicus, SMOS), and anthropogenic factors (CSTB BDNB).
2. **Local Data Storage (3SES Data Lake):** Processed and derived data are stored in a centralized repository composed of two primary elements:
 - a. **PostGIS Database:** Used for storing vector data, standardized metadata, and spatial indices, supporting efficient geospatial querying.
 - b. **Object Storage (S3):** Used for large raster files such as GeoTIFFs, map tiles, and service backups.

9.3.3. Application Layer – FastAPI Backend

The application layer is implemented using **FastAPI**, a modern Python framework for building high-performance web APIs. FastAPI forms the core of the 3SES web service and offers several groups of endpoints.

9.3.3.1. API Surface

The backend exposes a concise but expressive set of API endpoints, for example:

- Authentication-related endpoints that help validate EOSC tokens and expose user profile information as needed by the frontend,
- Risk query endpoints where clients can submit a location, an area, or a scenario and receive corresponding shrink–swell risk indicators,
- Map-oriented endpoints that provide vector or tile-based representations of risk layers,
- Dataset and metadata endpoints that describe the available FAIR data products, their versions and provenance.

These APIs communicate primarily using JSON and are documented with OpenAPI, benefiting from FastAPI's built-in documentation support.

9.3.3.2. Business Logic and Risk Engine Integration

Within the backend, a dedicated set of services implements the business logic of 3SES. These services:

- Integrate with the underlying risk engine or modelling components to obtain raw risk outputs,
- Convert the raw outputs into user-facing indicators and categories,
- Combine static conditioning factors (such as soil type) with dynamic triggering factors (such as climate scenarios),
- Apply classification rules, thresholds and symbology definitions that will be used in the frontend map visualisation.

This separation ensures that the mapping from scientific outputs to user-oriented risk products is transparent and maintainable.

9.3.3.3. *Data Access and Performance Considerations*

FastAPI services interact with the 3SES data services through well-defined repositories and query interfaces. Where appropriate, the backend may pre-generate or cache tiles and aggregates, so that high-traffic map requests can be served efficiently.

9.3.3.4. *Presentation Layer – Next.js Frontend*

The presentation layer is built with **Next.js**, a React-based framework that supports both server-side rendering (SSR) and static site generation (SSG). This choice provides a responsive user experience and good performance for map-heavy pages.

9.3.3.4.1. *User Interface and Navigation*

The web portal offers a set of views tailored to the main user activities, for example:

- A landing page introducing the service and providing access to the main map.
- A map dashboard where users can select locations, view risk information and explore layers.
- Optional expert views that expose more detailed controls for scenario selection, temporal comparisons or sensitivity analysis.
- User-centric pages, such as saved locations or downloaded reports.

Navigation is intentionally simple, guiding non-expert users directly to relevant maps while still giving experts room to explore.

9.3.3.4.2. *Map Viewer and Layer Management*

At the core of the interface is the **map viewer**, which uses an OpenStreetMap-based map provider as the base layer. On top of this base map, the frontend displays:

- Shrink–swell risk layers delivered as tiles or vector overlays,
- Additional contextual layers (administrative boundaries, infrastructure, etc.),
- Legends and colour scales that help interpret the risk categories.

Layer visibility, transparency and ordering can be controlled by the user via intuitive controls.

9.3.3.4.3. Federated Login and Role-Aware UI

The frontend integrates with EOOSC AAI via OIDC. On login, the Next.js application receives tokens and decodes the claims that are relevant for user identification and role assignment. Based on these roles, the UI selectively enables or hides certain features:

- Public users may only see generalised layers and basic information,
- Authenticated citizens see more detailed information for their assets,
- Experts or data providers gain access to advanced tools and configuration pages.

9.4. BDAnalytics

BDAnalytics is proposed as an open-source service for climate impact analysis, designed to overcome the limitations of current State-of-the-Art (SoTA) Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning²² (DL) methods, unlike traditional fully supervised models that require extensive labeled datasets and high computational resources for retraining, BDAnalytics utilizes a Multimodal Multi-Domain Self supervised (MMDS) Model²³.

This service can handle regressions, classification (e.g., land cover, soil type), segmentation (e.g., flood inundation), and detection (e.g., wildfire) tasks while requiring approximately **10% of the computational resources** of traditional approaches. It integrates directly with the **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC** component to ingest FAIR data and provides analytical support to the other project services (OPENHIDRA, 3SES, and Just-CURS).

9.4.1. High Level System Architecture

The **BDAnalytics** architecture is built around a central AI engine that processes standardized input data to generate predictive models and reports. A visualisation of the architecture of BDAnalytics in Figure 16.

- **Input Layer:** The system accepts user queries defining specific tasks (e.g., "segmentation of flood areas") and retrieves the necessary FAIR-compliant data from **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC**.
- **Core Processing (MMDS):** The core of the architecture is the MMDS model, which combines Large Vision Models (LVMs) for image analysis and Large Language Models (LLMs) for textual/metadata interpretation.
- **Infrastructure:** The service is initially planned to deploy on **EOOSC cloud resources**

²² Zhang, Y., et al. (2024). "Vision beyond boundaries: An initial design space of domain-specific large vision models in human-robot interaction." Adjunct Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Mobile Human-Computer Interaction, 1-8.

²³ Li, J., et al. (2022). "Deep Learning in Multimodal Remote Sensing Data Fusion: A Comprehensive Review." arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.01380.

in the future months using containerization (Docker/Kubernetes) to ensure scalability and reproducibility across heterogeneous infrastructure. The system operates in a self-supervised manner, allowing the base model to be "frozen" and used as a feature extractor, significantly reducing the time required for fine-tuning specific user cases

Figure 16 BDAnalytics Architecture

9.4.2. Data Architecture and Federation Model

BDAnalytics relies on the project's federated data architecture to access training and inference data.

- **Data Ingestion:** The service does not store raw data permanently; instead, it pulls data "on-demand" from the **CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC** service. This ensures that all input data (satellite imagery, climate models, in-situ observations) has already passed through the FAIRification pipeline and possesses valid metadata and Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).
- **Data Split:** For model development, the architecture manages datasets by splitting them into training (70%), validation (10%), and testing (20%) sets to ensure robust performance.
- **Output Storage:** Analytical results and generated models are packaged as FAIR Digital Objects and stored in EOSC-connected repositories, ensuring they are discoverable via the project's knowledge graph.

9.4.3. Data-Adapters

As a consumer within the ecosystem, **BDAnalytics** utilizes **FAIRification Pipeline** to mediate data exchange.

- **Ingestion Adapter**
A specialized adapter connects to the CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC interface. This adapter is responsible for authenticating with the internal service to access both

open and restricted FAIR datasets and converting the retrieved FAIR digital objects into machine learning ready formats required for the Multimodal Multi-Domain Self Supervised (MMDS) model.

- **Pre-processing**

Internal adapters perform cleaning and pre-processing on gigapixel satellite images and metadata before they are fed into the neural networks.

9.4.4. Application Layer

The application layer hosts the complex ML/DL logic and optimization routines.

Model Construction: This layer manages the instantiation of **CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks)**²⁴ and **Transformer-based models**.²⁵ It applies specific optimizers (e.g., SGD, Adam) and loss functions (e.g., cross-entropy, focal loss) to train the models.

- **Task-Specific Modules:** The application logic branches into four distinct processing paths based on the user query:
- **Regression** (Trend analysis)
- **Classification** (Land use/cover)
- **Segmentation** (Disaster mapping)
- **Detection** (Change detection).

Report Generation: A **Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)**²⁶

mechanism is implemented within the LLM components to generate detailed, human-readable reports explaining the analytical results.

9.4.5. Presentation Layer

The user interaction is managed through a GUI integrated into the EOOSC environment.

- **User Interface:** Users can interact with the service to define their own cases (customise) or select from pre-defined models. The interface allows users to specify the type of analysis (e.g., "Forecasting future climate scenarios" or "Risk of clay shrinkage").
- **Visualisation:** The presentation layer visualizes the output of the LVMs (e.g., segmented maps of coastal areas) and displays the text reports generated by the

²⁴ Zhu, X. X., et al. (2017). "Deep Learning in Remote Sensing: A Comprehensive Review and List of Resources." IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine, 5(4), 8-36.

²⁵ Vaswani, A., et al. (2017). "Attention Is All You Need." Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems-30, Vaswani, A., et al. (2017). "Attention Is All You Need." Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 30.

²⁶ Lewis, P., et al. (2020). "Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks." Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 33, 9459-9474.

LLMs.

- **EOSC Integration:** The service interface is accessible via the EOSC Marketplace, utilizing Federated AAI for single sign-on capabilities.

10. EOOSC Integration

The integration of the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC project into the European Open Science Cloud (EOOSC) should follow the principles outlined in the EOOSC Federation Handbook²⁷. Either as a candidate EOOSC node or onboarding data/services into an existing EOOSC node, Climate-Adapt4EOOSC will adopt an architecture to ensure interoperability with the EOOSC EU Node and other national, thematic or regional nodes. Moreover, and for this integration, will be implemented the mandatory federating capabilities. This means that it will adopt the Federated Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), monitoring, accounting, and service management, which allow the project resources to be discoverable and accessible via the central EOOSC Resource Hub. Either operating as an integrated node or onboarding into an existing EOOSC node, the project will contribute to EOOSC FAIR data and services that enables cross-domain discovery and access to the project outputs.

The integration strategy is two-fold, presenting two parallel options:

- **Establish a dedicated Climate-Adapt4EOOSC EOOSC Node:** deploying a new thematic node with complete EOOSC-compliant infrastructure.
- **Onboard Climate-Adapt4EOOSC services into an existing EOOSC Node:** using an established EOOSC node with the established infrastructure and services.

Both approaches need to line up with EOOSC standards, including the EOOSC Interoperability Framework (EOOSC-IF) technical, semantic, legal, and organisational guidelines, to ensure that can be integrated smoothly with EOOSC. Below, we detail each strategy covering the platform architecture (SMP Agents and SIMPL-Open middleware), federated AAI integration, FAIRification pipelines, metadata harvesting processes, and compliance with EOOSC interoperability requirements. But to take advantage of the project capabilities and contribute meaningfully to the ecosystem, the primary strategy is to establish a dedicated Climate-Adapt4EOOSC node.

10.1. Architecture and EOOSC Alignment

For the integration into EOOSC, the platform is built as a modular system that integrates Simpl-Open and Simpl-Open Middleware Agents (SMP Agents) to bridge external data sources, enforce FAIR data practices, and expose standardised interfaces for EOOSC compatibility. To address the need for bi-directional communication with EOOSC harvesters the architecture exposes standardised interfaces (OAI-PMH or DCAT compliant endpoints).

Climate-Adapt4EOOSC uses Simpl-Open as the core integration layer to interconnect with various data spaces. SMP Agents act as intelligent proxies or gateways that securely ingest

²⁷ EOOSC Association. (2025). EOOSC Federation Handbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999577>

data streams from the data sources and expose them to the platform. Each SMP agent connects with an external provider, handling data transfer protocols, enforcing security policies, and performing any necessary transformations. This design allows the platform to federate data into EOOSC and makes the project outputs available to all the nodes. Once data is fetched, via SMP Agents, it is normalised and stored in the storage layer for further processing.

The authentication system is designed to integrate with EOOSC federated AAI. Deploying an OpenID Connect (OIDC) compatible identity management solution enabling the EOOSC AAI federation users to log in to services with their institutional or EOOSC credentials via Single Sign-On. This allows the enforcement of role-based access control (RBAC) on federated user attributes and roles. This federated AAI setup is a mandatory requirement for EOOSC integration, so the authentication is interoperable across the EOOSC ecosystem.

All incoming data and new datasets pass through a FAIRification pipeline to meet EOOSC FAIR data principles. As new datasets or results from services are ingested (often via SMP Agents), the platform systematically standardises the metadata and formats. Local metadata is mapped to EOOSC-compliant schemas, and during this ingestion process, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) such as DOIs or Handles are minted or assigned to every asset (datasets, tools, models). Assigning PIDs ensures each resource can be reliably referenced and linked within EOOSC. The FAIRification workflow transforms data into standardised, machine-readable datasets with enriched metadata, ready for discovery and reuse.

Climate-Adapt4EOOSC will maintain a metadata catalogue of all its resources (datasets and services) exposed through standard harvesting endpoints. For example, the platform can provide an OAI-PMH (or a REST API following DCAT-AP), allowing EOOSC harvesting services to find and collect Climate-Adapt4EOOSC metadata periodically. This ensures the integration with the EOOSC Metadata Knowledge Graph, that act as the central EOOSC catalogue.

To support the technical interoperability, all Climate-Adapt4EOOSC services (e.g., climate data analysis tools, models, and workflows) will implement open standard interfaces and EOOSC compliant protocols. Data services implement widely used web service standards (for example, RESTful JSON APIs or SPARQL endpoints where appropriate). In the alignment with EOOSC EU node architecture, the project will also integrate with EOOSC Execution Framework (EEF)²⁸. The EEF provides a federated orchestration layer for running workloads across distributed Cloud, HPC, and Kubernetes environments. This ensures that Climate-Adapt4EOOSC services can execute workloads in a reproducible, traceable, and policy-compliant manner across EOOSC managed resources.

All project services (including BDAnalytics, OPENHIDRA, 3SES, and Just-CURS) will expose an OpenAPI (Swagger) specifications and accessible through the platform API gateway.

28 paolo, . manghi ., Brandt, C., Caballer, M., Kołomański, M., Moltó, G., Bardi, A., & Mantes, T. (2025). EOOSC Beyond D13.1 First release of the EOOSC Execution Framework V1.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045756>

This enable external EOSC services or workflows to programmatically orchestrate or invoke Climate-Adapt4EOSC tools/data. For example, a dataset hosted by Climate-Adapt4EOSC could be included in a Jupyter notebook or used by an EOSC workflow platform, feeding a model hosted on a different EOSC node.

Throughout its architecture, Climate-Adapt4EOSC uses EOSC-IF guidelines, which define interoperability across four dimensions: technical, semantic, legal, and organisational. Technically, as noted, the platform uses open protocols and machine-actionable APIs and issues PIDs to ensure all resources can be readily discovered and linked. Semantic interoperability is attained with controlled vocabularies and community ontologies in metadata, ensuring that descriptions share common terminology (e.g., standard keywords, units) so they can be understood across domains. Legal interoperability is addressed by clearly defining usage licences for data, tools and compliance with regulations such as GDPR for any personal or sensitive data, and this includes providing proper data/service use agreements and consent where required. Organisational interoperability involves aligning with EOSC governance: the project commits to EOSC Rules of Participation and service-level agreements (SLAs). Building in compliance with these four dimensions ensures it can federate project resources within EOSC, meaning other nodes and users can integrate its services without technical or policy barriers.

With this architecture, Climate-Adapt4EOSC is well prepared to be integrated into EOSC via either approach, either onboarding to an existing node or deploying a new node, highlighting how the architecture and processes differ for each path.

10.2. Establishing a Dedicated EOSC Node

The project aims to operate autonomously as a node that peers with other nodes in the EOSC Federation. To achieve this integration needs to operate the full stack of EOSC federated services, including the EOSC Core capabilities, but it offers maximum control and visibility over the project services. Operating a dedicated node means full responsibility for meeting EOSC interoperability requirements and federating capabilities, which Climate-Adapt4EOSC addresses through its architecture. Deploying these core components will effectively mirror what EOSC EU node and other nodes provide but tailored to the project resources. To accelerate and establish immediate compliance the project will use well-tested solutions^{29 30}, specifically instancing the standard EOSC Resource Catalogue and the Helpdesk templates, ensuring the interoperability with the other EOSC nodes.

29 EOSC Beyond, *Deployment packages*, Retrieved December 3, 2025 from <https://docs.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/Deployment%20Packages/>

30 paolo, . manghi ., Brandt, C., Caballer, M., Kołomański, M., Moltó, G., Bardi, A., & Mantes, T. (2025). EOSC Beyond D13.1 First release of the EOSC Execution Framework V1.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17045756>

The node must provide its own authentication and authorisation service that connects to the EOOSC AAI Federation. In practice, Climate-Adapt4EOOSC would deploy an Identity Provider/Proxy (for example, a Keycloak server or similar) configured to trust and be trusted by the EOOSC AAI (via SAML and/or OIDC federation). This setup allows users to log in to the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC portal using their institutional or EOOSC identities, achieving Single Sign-On across EOOSC.

A dedicated node must run monitoring probes and accounting systems that integrate with EOOSC central monitoring. This would include tools such as ARGO (EOOSC monitoring framework) and other standard Nagios probes (or OpenSearch) to continuously track the health and availability of its services. It would also record usage metrics, for instance, how often datasets are downloaded, which tools are run, and for how long. These metrics are then reported to the central EOOSC Monitoring and Accounting services. Its uptime and reliability are visible, and resource usage is accounted for in EOOSC usage reports. This is crucial for SLA compliance; operating as a node means committing to specific service levels, and monitoring ensures they are met or that any issues are reported.

As a node, Climate-Adapt4EOOSC will maintain its own resource catalogue and guarantee it is harvestable by the EOOSC Hub. The node must implement or deploy a metadata catalogue solution that registers all Climate-Adapt4EOOSC resources and exposes the local catalogue to EOOSC harvesters. The EOOSC-IF technical requirements mandate that the node metadata be structured for automated discovery. Thus, the node catalogue will publish DCAT-AP 3.0 records with PIDs via an open endpoint. The central EOOSC Metadata Knowledge Graph will harvest records from the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC node on a schedule, integrating them into the global EOOSC search index.

The node needs to deploy its data and processing services in accordance with the EOOSC-IF interoperability guidelines. This means the hosting service backend should orchestrate data retrieval, keeping it separated from presentation logic (a good practice for interoperability). Any data or services would be containerised and exposed via the node API gateway with open standards. The goal is that other EOOSC tools or workflows can consume any service running on the node without custom adaptation. For example, if a workflow needs climate data, it could call the Climate-Adapt4EOOSC node API directly and use it directly in an analysis pipeline. Adhering to standard interfaces and data formats is critical here.

Operating a node also entails enforcing strong security and compliance measures. The node deployment would be configured to meet EOOSC security baseline requirements, including implementing proper user data privacy (GDPR compliance for how user data and logs are stored and managed), securing all service endpoints (HTTPS, vulnerability management), and ensuring incident response procedures align with EOOSC security policies. EOOSC Nodes are expected to maintain a high level of trust, and all data handling must respect licence agreements and ethical use (for instance, if specific datasets have restrictions, the node enforces those restrictions in its AAI and data access policies).

As a EOSC node, Climate-Adapt4EOSC will need to provide user support and service management consistent with EOSC practices. This may include running a helpdesk or ticketing system and maintaining documentation and training materials for its services. It also involves establishing operational procedures for incident management, resource provisioning, and updates so that the node services remain reliable.

Operating a dedicated node means full responsibility for meeting EOSC interoperability requirements and federated capabilities, which Climate-Adapt4EOSC addresses through its architecture. Deploying these core components, the deployed node will effectively mirror what the EOSC EU Node and other nodes provide, but with a thematic focus on climate adaptation resources.

10.3. Onboarding into an Existing EOSC Node

While establishing a dedicated node is the primary objective, onboarding Climate-Adapt4EOSC resources into an existing EOSC node serves as contingency strategy, means registering its services and resources with a pre-existing EOSC node (thematic, national, or regional). In this scenario, Climate-Adapt4EOSC becomes a service provider within that node rather than running a standalone EOSC infrastructure, taking advantage of the host node infrastructure for federated services. This scenario ensures that the project outputs remain accessible via EOSC even if the dedicated node deployment face unforeseen infrastructure delays. Although it requires strict architectural alignment to the host rules, interfaces, and validation procedure.

To successfully onboard, Climate-Adapt4EOSC must align with the technical foundations expected by the EOSC node. The project access management must be compatible with the host node AAI to ensure that a researcher logging in via the host EOSC node portal or via EOSC credentials can access Climate-Adapt4EOSC tools without a separate account. The platform RBAC should consume EOSC-provided user attributes (such as group memberships or roles) so that single sign-on and role dependency access are in place across both the host node and Climate-Adapt4EOSC services.

All Climate-Adapt4EOSC services must expose open standard APIs as described earlier (REST/JSON endpoints, OGC web services, SPARQL, etc.) so that the host EOSC node can easily integrate and advertise these services. These standard protocols allow services to be invoked via the host node interfaces or integrated into EOSC workflows. Moreover, high technical readiness is required, as services should be at technology readiness level (TRL) 7 or above, meaning they are stable, well-tested, and scalable for production use. This assures the host node that onboarding these services will not compromise reliability or user experience.

Climate-Adapt4EOSC resources need to be described with EOSC-compliant metadata. Using DCAT-AP 3.0 for datasets and appropriate metadata profiles for software/tools, the

project ensures each resource has a rich, machine-readable description. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) must be in place for datasets, software, and even for major workflows, enabling traceability and citation. The platform should expose its metadata through endpoints that the host node catalogue can harvest. In alignment with the EOSC-IF semantic guidelines, metadata should include standardised fields (title, description, keywords, etc.) and use controlled vocabularies to maximise cross-disciplinary discovery.

The data architecture must ensure that any dataset provided by Climate-Adapt4EOSC is accessible via standard protocols and that access policies (open or controlled) are clearly defined. If specific data requires authentication, the integration with the EOSC AAI will handle that. For tools and models, the availability of an OpenAPI description means EOSC Tool/Workflow repositories can link to them and even execute them if integrated with a workflow manager. In short, onboarding requires that everything must be plugged into the open EOSC and accessible by other nodes.

Additionally, by choosing an existing node with established federated capabilities, Climate-Adapt4EOSC can use the host operational services. The host node likely already has in place monitoring and accounting, service management and support, and established processes, as it will have experience onboarding services, so it can provide guidance and standardised workflows for registering and validating new services. This reduces the integration burden on the project by following an alternative path of establishing and running a ECOS Node.

11. CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC KPI Definition

11.1. WP1 Requirement Analysis and Architecture for future proofing EOOSC integration

Table 3 KPIs for Work Package 1

KPI/Task	Status	Comment
KP1 Online meeting with the Stakeholder forum by M6	Accomplished	Meeting held on September 8th 2025: https://climate-adapt4eoosc.eu/event/workshop-eliciting-the-existing-value-proposition-architecture-and-future-proofing-of-eoosc-infrastructure/
KP2 At least 15 data spaces have been studied for possible integration	Accomplished	>20 data spaces have been studied, 3 UCs data sources, national data spaces, EU Common data spaces have been reviewed
KP3 Requirements of these four services are analysed	In Progress	3 UCs input dataset matrix prepared, datasets are being investigated for understating for one common system architecture (ex. D1.1, D1.2)

11.2. WP2 CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC: Data Providers and interoperability for the Exchange and for the EOOSC-core

Table 4 KPIs for Work Package 2

KPI/Task	Status	How Achieved	Comment
KPI4: At least 15 data adapters are developed	Not Started		
KPI5: At least 3 tools for extracting mandatory metadata are developed	Not Started		
KPI6: Robust mapping engine is created which works 50% more efficiently than the SoA approach	Not Started		

KPI7: The entity matching tool is validated by using at least 8 different data sets.	Not Started
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11.3. WP3 Organisational and legal interoperability of services and data

Table 5 KPIs for Work Package 3

KPI/Task	Status	How Achieved	Comment
KPI8: A discussion with at least with 15 institutes has been undertaken to understand organisational and legal issues of data sharing	In Progress		Most of the pilot use case partners have been consulted (dedicated workshops with UC1 and UC3), UC2 and replicators to follow
KPI9: At least 3 collaborative work with EU standardization institutes for integration of open climate data thresholds into the future norms/standards	Not Started		Pending completion of KPI9
KPI10: Two interoperability frameworks (Organisational and legal) are developed and consulted with the EOSC Task force	In Progress		Work on D3.1 will contribute to this KPI, the EOSC Symposium 2025 and the RDA Europe Summit 2025 have provided additional background information.

11.4. WP4 CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOSC: Service Providers and interoperability for the Exchange and for the EOSC-core

Table 6 KPIs for Work Package 4

KPI/Task	Status	How Achieved	Comment
KPI11: Two interoperability frameworks have been submitted to the EOSC-IF	Not Started		
KPI12: 3 new services developed, tested and validated on 3 real use cases each across Europe	Not Started		
KPI13: The BDAnalytics reduce 90% resources with 95% more accuracy in analysis compared to the SoA techniques	Not Started		

11.5. WP5 Demonstration and replication of CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOSC and CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOSC to the stakeholders and EU member States

Table 7 KPIs for Work Package 5

KPI/Task	Status	How Achieved	Comment
KPI14: Three rounds of demonstration have been performed	Not Started		
KPI15: At least 50 relevant stakeholders have been reached through CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC solutions	Not Started		

11.6. WP6 Road map, recommendations, sustainability and liaison with EOSC, its partnership and other related climate adaptation mechanisms

Table 8 KPIs for Work Package 6

KPI/Task	Status	How Achieved	Comment
KPI16: The final road map is consulted with the advisory board and stakeholder forum	Not Started		
KPI17: 3 EU policy briefs relating to each of the 3 services for their implementation at the European level is drafted	Not Started		
KPI18: At least 10 actionable recommendations are generated to improve sustainability and liaison with EOSC, its partnership and other related climate adaptation mechanisms.	Not Started		

12. Risk and Mitigation Measure

12.1. SIMPL Open Middleware Platform

SIMPL-Open is an active and continuously developing initiative. As the project evolves, its specifications, workflows, and integration patterns are still being refined. Within CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC, we are in the process of evaluating how SIMPL-Open fits with our architectural and interoperability needs, and how its capabilities align with our planned data-sharing workflows.

The main risk is that SIMPL-Open may not fully meet the functional or operational requirements of CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC within the necessary project timeframe. This could affect how we connect to the Dataspace or manage contract negotiation across providers and consumers.

Mitigation:

If SIMPL-Open does not meet the required level of readiness for our use cases, CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC will adopt a fallback approach using individual EDC connectors to interact directly with the Dataspace. Under this method, contract negotiation may need to be handled manually, but it ensures that the project can proceed without interruption and remain compatible with future SIMPL-Open developments.

12.2. FAIRification pipeline

The FAIRification pipeline aims to standardise and enrich heterogeneous datasets so they become Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Because data is sourced from different organisations and formats, the level of metadata completeness and consistency may vary. This creates a risk that some datasets cannot be fully processed through the automated FAIRification steps, requiring additional manual work. Another risk is that not all providers use the same vocabularies or metadata standards, which can slow down semantic alignment and interoperability.

Mitigation:

To reduce these risks, CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOOSC will use a step-by-step FAIRification approach. All providers will first supply a minimal, harmonised metadata template, ensuring that every dataset can enter the pipeline. Where automatic mapping is not possible, manual checks will be introduced to maintain quality. Clear guidelines, shared vocabularies, and reusable metadata examples will be provided to partners, along with mappings across vocabularies and standards, to support consistency. The pipeline will remain modular so that new tools or converters can be added as needed without disrupting existing workflows.

12.3. EOOSC Onboarding and Integration

Joining a big federation like EOOSC and setting up complex data services is not without its challenges. Climate-Adapt4EOOSC has spotted some of these risks and come up with plans to tackle them, making sure everything goes smoothly:

- **Evolving Standards Risk:** EOOSC technologies, APIs, and standards may change (e.g., new versions of metadata schemas or changes to AAI protocols). This could render some integration components outdated.

Mitigation: The Climate-Adapt4EOOSC architecture is modular and loosely coupled. Each component (authentication, catalogue, data service, etc.) can be updated or replaced with minimal impact on others. By following open standards and avoiding proprietary solutions, the project can adapt to any EOOSC requirement updates.

- **Federated AAI Integration Complexity:** Connecting to a federated AAI (potentially with dozens of identity providers and authorisation flows) is complex and can lead to integration issues (e.g., mismatches in user attributes or login errors).

Mitigation: Early prototyping and testing of its AAI integration with EOOSC test environments. By working closely with EOOSC AAI experts (for instance, EGI Federation AAI support teams), the project can debug issues well before production. Clear documentation of user roles and attributes in the platform ensures consistency. The use of a well-supported tool like Keycloak, which is common in EOOSC, also reduces risk, as it is a proven solution.

- **Data Heterogeneity and Quality:** The project aggregates climate data from many sources; differences in format, quality, or metadata completeness make FAIRification and interoperability difficult.

Mitigation: Detailed definition of schemas and mapping templates for each data source type. The FAIRification pipeline includes validation steps, for example, checking that required metadata fields are present, and values conform to expected vocabularies. Any dataset that does not meet quality thresholds will not be published until corrected. Continuous improvement of mappings (with feedback from data consumers) will ensure the integrated data remains interoperable and useful.

- **Performance and Scalability:** Under the EOOSC federation, the exposure could lead to high demand. Services might face heavy load if many users across Europe simultaneously access climate tools or download large datasets.

Mitigation: The architecture is built with scalability in mind, using containerised services orchestrated by Kubernetes that can scale out horizontally when usage

spikes. Caching mechanisms are put in place. Regular load testing is planned to identify bottlenecks and optimise the system before real users hit it.

- **Security and Compliance:** Operating within EOSC means any security incident or data breach could have wider implications due the interconnection of the nodes, and non-compliance with data protection regulations could harm service reliability.

Mitigation: Following DevSecOps best practices, embedded in the development and deployment cycle. Automated security scans, dependency checks, and prompt patching of vulnerabilities. Periodic security audits and security assessments to ensure all best practices are met. Transparent user consent processes and access logs are maintained to provide accountability.

The architecture alignment with EOSC standards and the dual strategy ensure the project can adapt to the most feasible path while EOSC Nodes develops, supporting the successful CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC integration of the outputs into the EOSC ecosystem.

13. Conclusion

This deliverable has set out the overall Climate-Adapt4EOOSC architecture, described how data flows from diverse local, national, European and international sources through the common middleware platform, FAIRification pipeline, and intermediate schema into CLIMATE-ADAPTdata4EOOSC, and how this data goes to the four services in CLIMATE-ADAPTservice4EOOSC. It has also mapped a detailed KPI framework across all work packages, clarified roles for data providers and consumers, and outlined the mechanisms for EOOSC integration, including dedicated and shared node options. Together, these elements provide a technical and organisational blueprint for delivering FAIR, interoperable climate adaptation data and services.

This deliverable also highlights key challenges such as heterogeneous access policies and standards across data spaces, the need to mature legal and organisational interoperability frameworks, and the effort required to operationalise FAIRification and EOOSC onboarding at scale. The next steps focus on implementing and validating the toolkit components in real use cases, completing interoperability frameworks, executing demonstrations and replication activities, and using the KPI registry to monitor progress and steer improvements, ultimately leading to a sustainable, EOOSC-aligned Climate-Adapt4EOOSC ecosystem.

